

OX40 ligand (TNFSF4) in penetrating (fistulizing) Crohn's Disease.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

We utilized whole transcriptome technologies to identify genes whose expression define the Montreal B3, or fistulizing/penetrating phenotype of Crohn's Disease, a perianal variant of the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease, also known as fistulizing or penetrating Crohn's Disease, in which the intestinal wall is breached resulting in abnormal communication between adjacent luminal regions of the bowel wall, or between the bowel wall and the abdomen or perianal region. We previously reported discovery of the receptor for LIGHT, *TNFRSF14* as a gene whose expression defines the penetrating/fistulizing signature. and described stage-specific regulation of LIGHT in the human myeloid compartment by the minimal bacterial product muramyl dipeptide (MDP), demonstrating physiologic and pathologic function for a TNF superfamily receptor in penetrating CD. We also described a second TNF superfamily receptor that displayed preferential expression in the penetrating disease subtype, *TNFRSF1B*. Here we report identification of a third TNF superfamily gene expressed in the B3 fistulizing phenotype, the OX40 ligand encoded by *TNFSF4*. Thus, two TNF receptors and a TNF superfamily ligand are expressed in a manner that indicates potential for combined TNF superfamily therapeutic targeting as a viable clinical intervention for humans with penetrating CD.

References

1. Graham, D.S.C., Graham, R.R., Manku, H., Wong, A.K., Whittaker, J.C., Gaffney, P.M., Moser, K.L., Rioux, J.D., Altshuler, D., Behrens, T.W. and Vyse, T.J., 2008. Polymorphism at the TNF superfamily gene *TNFSF4* confers susceptibility to systemic lupus erythematosus. *Nature genetics*, 40(1), pp.83-89.
2. Jacquemin, C., Schmitt, N., Contin-Bordes, C., Liu, Y., Narayanan, P., Seneschal, J., Maurouard, T., Dougall, D., Davizon, E.S., Dumortier, H. and Douchet, I., 2015. OX40 ligand contributes to human lupus pathogenesis by promoting T follicular helper response. *Immunity*, 42(6), pp.1159-1170.
3. Takeda, I., Ine, S., Killeen, N., Ndhlovu, L.C., Murata, K., Satomi, S., Sugamura, K. and Ishii, N., 2004. Distinct roles for the OX40-OX40 ligand interaction in regulatory and nonregulatory T cells. *The Journal of Immunology*, 172(6), pp.3580-3589.